

A MODERN ANALYSIS OF THE PROBLEMS OF “EPISTEMOLOGICAL OPTIMISM AND SKEPTICISM”

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ABSTRACT

In philosophy, the problem of doubt in the process of knowing the world and truth. An important method of skepticism in knowledge. Passive acceptance of the current regime of things, ruling opinions and other ethical-political terms. Philosophical skepticism is a school of philosophical thought.

Key words: skepticism, knowledge, position, doubt, truth, method, relativity.

The problem of knowing the world is one of the important problems in philosophy. This practice has been practiced from the modern era to the present day, and in the course of the development of philosophy, all kinds of attitudes and opinions were formed: optimism, skepticism, agnosticism, and others. This is a part of what I want to talk about. I distinguish two different positions in understanding the world - epistemological optimism and epistemological pessimism. In the first position, it is believed that the world is open to a person, proportional to his cognitive ability, and there are no obstacles to its adequate understanding. Such faith was characteristic of such thinkers as Plato, Aristotle, B. Spinoza, G. Hegel, K. Marx and others.

Skepticism is distinguished from many manifestations in philosophy and has many representatives from the modern world to modern philosophy. Skepticism, as one of the orientations of philosophy or as a type of philosophical thought, appeared in the modern world, which experienced a long ideological and historical evolution and reached the peak of its existence. Skepticism in its most complete form is the skepticism of the world.¹

Taking into account the position of epistemological pessimism, on the contrary, it is impossible to simply say that the thinkers who led to this development have lost their ability to know the world. This is the most effective and interesting "pessimism" from the point of view of epistemology, because it does not promote knowledge, but rather it is learned, it says that knowledge is a composite and multifaceted gift, which is worthy of special attention. In order to specify the phenomenon of scientific pessimism, the terms skepticism and agnosticism began to be used interchangeably.

¹ Д.А. Гусеев-Античный скептицизм как ранняя форма рефлексии теоретического знания. М:2010.

Skepticism (Greek - observation, verification) is a position that promotes skepticism as a principle of theoretical thinking, in particular, doubt about the possibility of attaining reliable and true knowledge about the truth. This position originates from modern skepticism (Pyrrhus, Aenesidemus, Empiricus), who formulated the thesis about the necessity of refraining from narrow-minded thinking and characterized the possibility of gaining only reliable knowledge. In the future, skepticism will take on various external manifestations, and it will show itself in the form of criticism, not taking anything for granted, putting everything under suspicion and offering to try one's strength.

The emergence of skepticism is closely related to the fact that there are practical and ethical issues in the minds of thinkers who are engaged in the theoretical study of existence and thought, nature and society as a result of the crisis caused by the society. What should be the nature of a person, so that he can get rid of everything that can make him restless? The greatest importance is given to research and its theoretical application to this question. Not only social life, but also the interest in learning the absolute truth and learning about the world will decrease. This is one of the most important conditions that contributed to the emergence and spread of skepticism.¹

At the same time, many philosophers in different eras set themselves the problem of knowing the truth and searching for a true and complete view of things. Descartes, Leibniz, Kant, Bacon and others presented their theories about the nature of the world. Experience can only provide true knowledge if it is free from false idols. "Idols of species" are mistakes that are realized as a result of values based on comparing human nature to human society; "cave idols" are mistakes of an individual nature, depending on the upbringing, taste, and habits of people; "market idols" are the habits of using current ideas and opinions without a critical attitude to the world; "Idols of the theater" is related to the visionary faith in the government.² Some of the schools advanced the knowledge based on the senses, and some of the schools combined the rational knowledge and presented their methods accordingly. Each theory offers its own path and special principles, which show how a person should look at reality in order to accept it as its real, significant structural part. The methods of power changed, replaced each other, but in most cases they were against each other. Such a theory has not been created that unites all of its predecessors, creates a universal way of determining the meaning of things, their existential structural parts. One of the methods of knowledge is skepticism, which appeared in the early stages of the development of philosophy. From the time of Heraclitus, who said that "everything changes by itself", we have seen the constant relativity of all theories and things. To this day, this theory continues to

¹ В.М.Богуславский -Скептицизм в философии. М:1990

² Д.А. Гусев-Античный скептицизм и философия науки: диалог сквозь два тысячелетия М.2020

show its evidence. From time to time, there is a statement that has become the target of skepticism, which completely excludes all methods of knowledge: "For every theory and every thing, there are infinitely many points of view and opinions that can be against each other." We summarize the answer to skepticism in Descartes' method of knowledge: Skeptics are suspected for the sake of being suspected. I doubt that I will find the truth." It is possible to take the meaning of the term "skepticism" as equivalent to the concept of "skepticism", to have a non-believing attitude towards a gay thing, to have a non-believing attitude, to look critically at the possibility, correctness or truth of a gay thing. Skepticism in its first sense is characterized as "self-doubt, a philosophical orientation that criticizes the possibility of knowing objective truth."¹

Here, I would like to see the connection of skepticism with epistemological methods and its importance in the diversity of knowledge methods.

At present, there are many different philosophical theories and views in the world. Most of them are diametrically opposed to each other. In other words, if we come to the situation where we are surrounded by all kinds of opinions, this leads us to delusions. Descartes wrote about this: "A person is like a traveler lost in a grove. He should choose a destination and adapt to where it will lead. In other words, the philosopher invites us to choose one theory from a complete complex, to accept it a priori and to finally implement it. But it is impossible to use this method. We note that epistemology, as written by Plato, searches for the full meaning of things, their "idea". Let's offer skepticism there. By using this "method", we can quickly determine that all the theories surrounding us are relative. We cannot believe in the truth of any of them, because with the help of the others, it is possible to beat the first one. From this point of view, accepting any theory is like playing roulette. "Everything is relative," say skeptics. However, it would be appropriate to mention here that skepticism itself is a relative and a method of epistemology.

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¹ Д.А.Гусеев- Античный скептицизм в истории становление научного мышления. М.2013

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